

The Efficacy of Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) Use in Endodontic Surgery: A Comprehensive Literature Review

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Introduction

The main objective of endodontic treatment is to stop and seize pulpal/periapical pathosis followed by preservation and restoration of natural dentition. Nonetheless, a persistent periapical infection despite adequate orthograde endodontic treatment may threaten the prognosis of a tooth. In such circumstances, apical surgery has proved to be a comprehensive treatment option to save the tooth. Lately, interest in the use of platelet-derived materials to promote bone-defect healing in endodontic microsurgery is growing. Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) is a second generation of autologous platelet concentrations. Except for platelets, PRF also contains other blood particles—B and T lymphocytes, monocytes, neutrophils, and stem cells, as well as growth factors (such as the platelet-derived epidermal growth factor, platelet-derived growth factor, vascular endothelial growth factor, basic fibroblast growth factor, and transforming growth factor-beta. An important property of PRF is the prolonged release of growth factors at the application site, typically for more than 7 days. Growth factors and released cytokines stimulate the activity of osteoblasts. The release of growth factors. Moreover, expedites tissue regeneration by increasing the migration of fibroblasts. Unlike in other fields, reports on the effects of PRF in endodontic microsurgery are infrequent. There are studies including RCT, in vivo, in vitro and case report that have been conducted on PRF efficiency but the effectiveness of PRF remains debatable.

Method and Materials

An electronic search of studies published in English language in PUBMED, SCOPUS, SCIENCE DIRECT, and GOOGLE SCHOLAR from June 2014 to June 2023 was conducted using the keywords; bone healing, endodontic microsurgery, periapical surgery, platelet-rich fibrin, postoperative pain. A total of 321 articles were included in the title and abstract screening. After the application of exclusion and inclusion criteria, a total of 16 articles were included in the review.

Discussion

The ultimate goal of an endodontic surgical procedure is to help regenerate the periapical tissues that were affected by the infectious process, including the alveolar bone, cementum, and periodontal ligament. Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) reported by Choukroun et al. is a second-generation platelet-derived material that contains more growth factors than PRP. Unlike PRP, PRF is produced by single centrifugation of autologous blood without the addition of anticoagulants or thrombin, and three layers are obtained: RBC layer, Fibrin clot layer (PRF), and serum layer (PPP). The advantage of PRF over other available options for membranes and bone substitutes is the fact that it is an autologous easily obtained material, that serves not only as a physical barrier but also as a source of all the blood constituents essential for the physiological osseous healing process. It is a cost-effective biomaterial that efficiently and locally directs and accelerates the healing process by serving as a stable network for the migration of cells for neoangiogenesis and as a provider of all the molecular and cellular intervening factors while protecting the open wound from epithelial ingrowth. There are some limitations associated with the study, including the presence of systemic diseases that can represent one of the confounding factors that might influence the process of periapical healing. Moreover, the fact that smoking status also affects postoperative healing and operative discomfort should also be considered. Another limitation of our study is that the periapical lesion size was not standardized in the involved studies. The location of the lesions also plays an important part postoperatively. No study has evaluated the differences according to the application method after endodontic surgery, and further studies are needed to regulate whether there is a difference in the effects on the application method. Moreover, the age or sex of the patients are the factors that may affect the action of growth factors or healing status.

Results

Karan and Aricioğlu measured pre- and postoperative bone density and found no significant differences in postoperative density calculations among all groups (PRF and control group) ($P > 0.05$). In a study by Krishnaveni, assessment between Group 1 (PRP + β -Tricalcium Phosphate and Group 2 (PRF + β -TCP) displayed no significant difference at 6 months ($P = 0.434$) and 1 year ($P = 0.975$) postoperatively. Monga et al. compared bone healing between PRF and the control group. A significantly higher rate of healing was observed after 9 months in a group where PRF was used as a graft material (82.36%) as compared to the Group, where no graft material was added (60.12%) ($P = 0.040$). A study done by Singh et al. to evaluate periapical healing radiographically to estimate the size of lesion postoperatively found that significantly less area persisted in Group PRF was used as a graft material (0.05) as compared to control Group (0.2) at the follow-up period. Tiwari et al. and Karan and Aricioğlu compared PRF and control group and estimated change in the volume of periapical lesions healed 1 year after the endodontic surgery by CBCT. A case report by Fahda N et al. reported that in three cases, the use of A-PRF membrane resulted in the complete healing of peri-radicular tissue and the preservation of root canal-treated tooth. Soto-Peñaloza et al. evaluated postoperative pain and described a mean (standard deviation [SD]) value of 12.7 (8.5) at the test sites, which was lesser than the mean (SD) scores at the control sites (20.7 [16.3]). Meschi et al. evaluated pain with a mean (SD) value of 0.8 (1.04) at the test site and 1.4 (1.98) at the control group. Singh et al. reported the lowest number of swellings found in the PRF group compared to others in 1, 3, 6, and 9 months, respectively.

References

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Figure 1. Platelet concentrates' clinical preparation, types/classes, and clinical illustration/presentation of several platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) and leukocyte and platelet-rich fibrin (L-PRF) preparations (membranes). <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1944/11/8/1293>

Conclusion

Within the limitations of the current study, PRF showed promising results and was a beneficial addition to endodontic surgeries.